

BREAKING THE SILENCE: UNCOVERING THE DANGERS WITHIN
NIGHT

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Abstract. The article is aimed to identify the atrocities of evil done towards Jews by Nazi regime, and the novel *Night* by American-Romanian author Elie Wiesel reflects how the world's silence and ignorance resulted on the Jews morbid fate and pain they went through. As the work vividly demonstrates the Holocaust initiated during the WWII, exploration of the work as powerful testimony to the horrors of genocide and the enduring human spirit, enables readers to acquire the full comprehension of the work.

Keywords: Jews, genocide, holocaust, silence, testimony, dangers, tortutes.

The Holocaust, also known as the Shoah, was a genocide in which the Nazi authority and its allies murdered mercilessly about six million Jews in World War II. For many years, the Holocaust has been a topic of discussion in international literature, with numerous authors addressing the themes of suffering, loss, and survival. However, as the full scope of the Holocaust became better understood in the decades that followed, many writers began to address the event in their work. Some, like Elie Wiesel and Primo Levi, wrote firsthand accounts of their experiences in concentration camps, while others, like Art Spiegelman and Jonathan Safran Foer, used fiction and graphic novels to explore the legacy of the Holocaust.

Elie Wiesel, an American writer of Romanian origin wrote the "*Night*" trilogy that includes the novels "*Night*", "*Dawn*" and "*Day*". All of these novels are semi-autobiographical, since they are based on Wiesel's own experience of the Holocaust [1]. The first book "*Night*" depicts the story of Wiesel' life as a teenage boy, who is sent to concentration camps with family, then is separated from them, but survives from extermination. The *Night* represents the Jewish nation's unfortunate destiny, severe repressions and torture caused by indifference of the world.

Looking back to a historical reason why this book came to life it is important to know what the Holocaust is itself. The word *Holocaust* as a term

has its own history, being taken from the Greek language. It encompasses the words “holo” (whole) and “kaustos” (burned) and is used to describe a sacrificial offering burned on an altar. Then the meaning was transferred to nominate the process of mass extermination of the Jewish nation initiated by the Nazi regime during the WWII. The deeds of that time still make people flinch from the horrors [6]. In September 1939, the German army occupied the western half of Poland. German police soon forced thousands of Polish Jews from their homes and into ghettos, confiscated their properties. Then it began to move to other parts of Europe reaching Transylvania too, where Elie Wiesel lived with his family. All Jews living there were boarded forcefully to the train in which cattle had previously been transported and brought to Auschwitz concentration camp, then to Buchenwald. Wiesel describes the situation: *“Lying down was not an option, nor could we all sit down. We decided to take turns sitting. There was little air. The lucky ones found themselves near a window; they could watch the blooming countryside flit by.”* (Chapter 2, p 23). [5] While analyzing the work the historical context plays a great role, because the author touches real historical events, real pain that the Jewish nation endured during the Second World War. Probably this experience pushed Wiesel to write a novel that depicts the horror of that dark period.

Conversely, the *Night* is considered to be a memoir by critics as it is a kind of testimony by Elie Wiesel, who is felt disgust by Germans, insult, harsh treatment and even encounters death by Nazi soldiers. The protagonist of the novel is Eliezer, a teenager that totally represents Elie himself [2]. He was sent to the Auschwitz death camp with his family, but was separated from his mother and sisters, because in the camp Jews were divided according to their gender, age and health. Nevertheless, Eliezer was lucky as he could stay with his father, so could Wiesel. He witnessed an enormous bonfire where a great number of children were put into fire alive. Some babies had been tossed into the air and used as targets for machine guns. All Jews were made to wear striped pajamas; they were treated worse than any animal. The narrator was involved in majority trials that correspond to events experienced by the author. Even characters' names remained unchanged due to the fact that they were real people [4].

Furthermore, the story addresses social issues such as religion, nation-separatism and Nazi ideology that fanatically strives to establish the government consisting of only Aryan race that is thought to be a superior race among others. One of the main reasons why Jews were targets of hatred is that they consider Jews an inferior race and began to fully cross out the whole

nation from the world history. The Jewish people are quite religious but tortures they went through, gas chambers where their beloved ones suffocated and died broke the nation's belief in God [3]. They blame God for their morbid fate, for not hearing their voices for help. In the novel local people of Sighet had not even believed until they were in the death camps itself, rejected to the fact that this kind of events might happen to them. The habitants of the village naively thought that German soldiers had come in order to aid with evacuation to the safer territories, as the war was still on. There is an episode where one boy asks his father, *"Can this be true? This is the twentieth century, not Middle Ages. Who would allow such crimes to be committed? How could the world remain silent?"* (p 118) [5]. For them it was hard to accept what was going around in the death camps.

Finally, the author intends to highlight that silence is a major cause for the Jewish nation's misfortunate and constant torment. On one hand, Jews own muteness and obedience drove them to extermination. On the other hand, other countries – the world stayed quiet, did not rush for help, and did not take any single action towards tyranny of fascism, they decided to remain neutral. Elie Wiesel with the novel *Night* screams that people must take sides whether the side of vice or virtue. Neutrality enforces the oppressors, never victims.

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